

***Sultana's Dream* and the Vision of Sustainable Energy: An Ecofeminist Perspective**

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Abstract

The threat of climate change and environmental destruction is a constantly growing issue that experts consider the greatest menace to humanity in recent years. Although ideas of adopting policies regarding sustainable energy sources and tackling climate change have gained significant traction over the past few decades, visionaries over the last century sensed the growing need to seek out ecological balance. Among them, Rokeya Sakhawat Hossain is a notable voice on the benefits of sustainable energy sources and a green city in her feminist utopia *Sultana's Dream* (1905). In contrast to the world inching toward achieving Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by 2030, *Sultana's Dream* was a text ahead of its time, not just because of its ideas about women's empowerment, but also because it was a blueprint for achieving multiple SDGs. *Sultana's Dream* shows that urban development can be accomplished by working with nature, not destroying it. The text portrays a female-led Ladyland in tune with nature using sustainable energy to develop itself further, resulting in a prosperous, climate-friendly nation. Adopting an ecofeminist framework, this paper examines how *Sultana's Dream* predicted the importance of sustainable living, clean energy, and climate action 100 years ago and how her work is a testament to humanity's potential to rekindle the connection with nature and achieve the SDGs today. The researchers use the text *Sultana's Dream* as the primary data source and embrace critical analysis to connect

it with 21st-century issues like SDGs, sustainable energy resources, green cities, etc. They finally arrive at the conclusion that Rokeya Sakhawat Hossain's text functions as a roadmap toward achieving climate and environment-related SDGs and proves that eco-friendly cities and clean energy are attainable in the present context.

Keywords: *Sultana's Dream*, SDG, ecofeminism, sustainable energy, green city, climate change, nature

Introduction

Sultana's Dream (1905) was Rokeya Sakhawat Hossain's vision of a utopian society from her perspective as a woman living in British India in the early twentieth century. The subversion of gender roles and the portrayal of a peaceful, advanced society of Ladyland ruled by women in *Sultana's Dream* make it a crucial work in the field of feminist criticism and gender studies. The text also reflects Rokeya's multidimensional negotiations with social realities and problems of her time (Dasthakur, 284), making it fascinating to examine in the light of ecocriticism, psychoanalytical criticism, peace and conflict studies, Marxist criticism, etc. In addition, *Sultana's Dream* was a revolutionary piece of work, one that was ahead of its time and remains relevant today due to the idea of Ladyland, a female-dominated space where women worked in universities, marched against enemy forces, built and ran "manufactories, laboratories and observatories" (Hossain 14) and their presence in traditionally masculine spaces like scientific laboratories essentially gave them authority over the entire nation (Rajan 174). Interestingly, the technology used by the inhabitants of Ladyland is particularly futuristic when viewed from the eco-friendly, energy-saving

perspective of the 21st century. Tomar argues that a distinct feature of *Ladyland* is the fact that the women all coexist with nature in a synergistic and harmonious manner. The Queen (and her subjects) appear to treat nature with a degree of reverence and are grateful for all that nature yields, as opposed to feeling entitled to nature. Their philosophy can be summed up when the Queen tells Sultana, "We enjoy nature's gifts as much as we can," (Hossain 14). While the sheer extent of this nature-friendly technology may seem fantastical at times, with the rising threat of climate change and environmental destruction, Rokeya Sakhawat Hossain's text appears remarkably intuitive about the benefits of clean and sustainable energy.

According to a survey published by the World Economic Forum, climate action failure was identified as the most severe risk on a global scale for the year 2022, followed by extreme weather, with mentions of human environmental damage and natural resource crises being cited as well (McLennan et al. 7-8). With climate change threatening to rupture human civilization, it becomes clear that Begum's Rokeya's vision of clean and sustainable energy as well as an awareness of the needs of the environment is very much relevant today. There is a global attempt to reverse the damage done to the environment as well as the effects of climate change, which can be seen in initiatives such as the Paris Agreement, which was adopted during the United Nations Conference of the Parties in 2015 to enact multilateral climate change action to accelerate "the reduction of global greenhouse gas emissions" and achieve a climate neutral world (1). Moreover, it acknowledged the need to promote universal access to sustainable energy in developing countries by increasing

the deployment of renewable energy (2) and that significant effort would be needed to bring down greenhouse gas emissions and limit global warming to 1.5°C when compared to pre-industrial levels (3-4).

Furthermore, the UN established the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development alongside the Paris Agreement to take action against climate change. The most relevant (for the purpose of this paper) are the following Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs):

SDG 4	Quality education
SDG 6	Clean water and sanitation
SDG 7	Affordable and clean energy
SDG 11	Sustainable cities and communities
SDG 13	Climate action

This paper aims to use textual analysis to connect the implementation of environment-friendly technology and the use of sustainable energy resources in Ladyland to the SDGs being promoted today to take action against climate change and prevent further ecological degradation. It will do so by examining how *Sultana's Dream* functions as a roadmap toward achieving climate and environment-related SDGs in the present global context. Moreover, the paper will attempt to prove that climate action, green eco-friendly cities, and clean energy are attainable in the context of the Asian subcontinent, as well as the rest of the world at the present time.

The first chapter of the paper introduces the subject matter and topic, as well as the rationale of the research conducted. The second chapter studies the existing literature around *Sultana's Dream* and ecocriticism while placing the paper in the framework of ecofeminism. This is followed by a discussion of the text and its analysis from the ecofeminist perspective. The fourth chapter proves how *Sultana's Dream* can be viewed as a blueprint for achieving climate and environment-related SDGs and building eco-friendly cities that use clean energy. Finally, the fifth chapter will conclude with the findings and inferences of the research.

Women and Nature: Ecofeminism as an Intersect

The twenty-first century has seen radical changes in different aspects of humanity. This era of scientific, technological, and digital growth has found itself at the peak of progress and development. These advancements are taking place, in many cases though, at the cost of destroying nature and the environment. As a result, climate change and other natural disasters have become frequent visitors in this age of advancement and enhancement. Philosophers, critics, and activists are, therefore, keeping issues like Ecocriticism much into the discussion. Eco-critics raise their voices against climate change and others and try to make people aware of the “anthropocentric dualism [of] human/ nature” (Garrard 26).

Ecofeminism is a branch of ecocriticism where the condition of women and nature are found to be interconnected. “It is a heuristic that synthesizes the feminist movement and the ecological movement, arguing that the dominion of sexual, ethnic, and social minorities and the dominion of nonhuman nature are interrelated” (Schultermandl 173). The modern world has entered into a new age of economic as well as technological growth where

both women and nature serve as commodities. “The material resourcing of women and of nature are structurally interconnected in the capitalist patriarchal system” (Saleh xi). It is, therefore, the women who can be more conscious and careful about maintaining the ecological balance by reducing the threats to climate and share the drive to “save their livelihood and make their communities safe” more than men (Saleh xi).

As the world is facing more danger because of climate change and natural disasters, people are talking more about environmental issues. Many measures have been taken by policymakers at different levels to protect the environment and reduce the threat. In January 2016, a total number of seventeen Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) were adopted “to create a set of global goals, related with the environmental, political and economic challenges that we face as humanity” (Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs): Our history and close relationship). Among them, SDG 6: Clean water and sanitation, SDG 7: affordable and clean energy, SDG 11: Sustainable cities and communities, and SDG 13: Climate action are directly linked with a green environment and global development. Surprisingly enough, the sustainable developments that the world is talking about now, Rokeya Sakhawat Hossain had addressed them long before in her feminist science fiction *Sultana’s Dream* in the 19th century.

Sultana’s Dream, being the earliest feminist science fiction in the Indian subcontinent, attracted many readers to look deep into the text and find elements relevant to date. Many critics analyzed the story from different perspectives. For example, Susmita Roye in her study “Sultana’s Dream vs Rokeya’s Reality: A Study of One of the Pioneering Feminist Science Fictions”,

identifies Rokeya Sakhawat Hossain as one of the pioneers of feminist science fiction and puts her in alignment with Mary Shelley. Rokeya's involvement of ideas that are drawn from scientific inventions and innovations, conceptualizing a "fantastic and futuristic" Ladyland, and an emphasis on scientific experiments level the story in the category of science fiction (Roye 144).

Parallel to this, Fayeza Hasnat also considers the story as a utopian science fiction story and is inclined to analyze it from an Ecocritical perspective in her "Sultana's Utopian Awakening: An Ecocritical Reading of Rokeya Sakhawat Hossain's *Sultana's Dream*". Reflecting on the British Raj in India and the system of zenana as the context, she found the story to be quite ahead of its time. It works, she argues, as an awakening for the women of Rokeya's time as it reverses the traditional zenana system and thus challenges the patriarchal Muslim society.

While both Roye and Hasnat explore the feminine utopian urge in the manner of science fiction in the story, Abdulla Al Mamun finds the story to be representing the inactive or dysfunctional male power before female authority. Debali Mookerjea-Leonard, on the other hand, assesses the story to be an example of the use of science and technology for the betterment of humanity. The women in the 'Ladyland', as observed, not only signify the women in the outside world and the men inside, but it also shows how the innovations of science and technology can be applied in daily life to make it easier, which was quite an advanced thought for the time it was written.

Although research has been conducted on the feminist and ecocritical perspective of the text, connecting women and the environment together, no work has been found on connecting the

SDGs with *Sultana's Dream* while the story surprisingly provides a roadmap toward achieving some of the SDGs. Logically, therefore, the paper asks the following research question and tries to find out the connection between the innovations in the Ladyland of *Sultana's Dream* and the policies taken to attain sustainable development in the world by 2030: How far does the text function as a roadmap toward achieving climate and environment-related SDGs and prove that eco-friendly cities and clean energy are attainable in the present context?

***Sultana's Dream* as an Ecofeminist Text**

First published in 1905, *Sultana's Dream* was a turning point of sorts for literature written for women, about women, by women and remains so today, often used as a beacon for women's writing in South Asia (Azim and Zaman 8). Written during a time when Muslim women were kept locked away in the seclusion of the *zenana*, while also experiencing the dehumanising effects of colonialism and imperialism of the British Raj, the short story serves as an escapist fantasy as well as an expression of the untapped potential that women have to contribute meaningfully to their lives, communities, and the world at large.

The story revolves around the strange dream of the titular Sultana, a woman living in British India during the late nineteenth or early twentieth century. She dreams of being magically transported to a strange country and is met by an unfamiliar woman she first mistakes for her friend Sister Sara. This woman takes her on a tour of the country called "Ladyland" as it is ruled and run by women. In Ladyland, the men are kept in seclusion, while the women have created an idealized version of society: one with peace, justice, and goodwill, one that prioritizes scientific discovery and works toward progress, and exist in harmony with

other nations, as well as nature itself. The story falls under the science fiction genre as it features scientific advancements and technological elements that had not been discovered or become commonplace at that point in time, such as using heat from the sun, “air cars” (Hossain 13), running water, and artificial rainfall to combat extreme heat. Through the emphasis on scientific progress and the competitive zeal of the female scientists of the two universities of Ladyland (Hossain 8), it is evident that Rokeya Sakhawat Hossain is championing the cause of female education and gender equality that she is known for.

Furthermore, in the context of the colonial period during which *Sultana's Dream* was published, the text is viewed by critics as vocally anti-colonial. This can be seen through the policy of conflict and diplomacy of Ladyland, and how the women react when threatened by invading forces. As Sister Sara says, the women were physically weaker than men, so rather than through the use of arms, they defeated the invading army of men “by brain power” (Hossain 10). Instead of soldiers, the Queen places the female scientists at the forefront, who choose science and their wits instead of domination and brute force and defeat the opposing army. According to Ahmed, the technological wonders of Ladyland are possible because Queen and her scientists actively reject colonial violence. Besides using education to advance scientific and technological progress, these women also use it to subvert gender norms and reverse the gender-based power dynamics of their society. For Rokeya Sakhawat (and the Queen), education and the ability to outwit both enemy forces and the patriarchal social system is the ultimate act of empowerment, as it allows the women who exist in the intersection of marginalities to exercise power and agency. As women like Sultana in British

India would be marginalised by both the colonizers and the male-dominated society, they experience “double colonisation” (Ashcroft 23), which contrasts sharply against the empowered citizens of Ladyland who experience freedom, exercise their agency, and enjoy peace and prosperity. This was only possible through the initiatives of the Queen, who enjoyed and prioritised science and ordered all the women of the country to be educated (Hossain 7). Thus, a central theme of the story emerges: the role of education in empowering the doubly marginalised and giving a voice and agency to the subaltern.

While nature isn't addressed as vigorously in *Sultana's Dream*, it is inextricably linked to the scientific advancements, technological progress, and overall prosperity of Ladyland. Through scientific progress, their female citizens are able to maintain harmonious and balanced relationships with nature and their environment; one that is mutually beneficial to all parties involved. Sultana finds the path on the streets carpeted with soft moss and flowers, even mistaking them for a velvet cushion, and compares the place to a garden (Hossain, 4). This showcases a kind of “give-and-take” relationship with nature, where the citizens care for nature, and in turn, nature takes care of them.

More ingeniously, the scientists invented a balloon through which they could draw water from the atmosphere and store it in tubes or pipes, which prevented storms and allowed the nation to have a supply of water during dry weather. On the other hand, another group of scientists devised a means of storing heat from the sun and distributing it when needed. While disregarded as a “sentimental nightmare” (Hossain, 9) by the men of the country, these inventions are what saved Ladyland not only from invasion but also protected their environment from ruin.

Examining these inventions from a modern perspective reveals these inventions to be a precursor of hydroelectric and solar power, two sustainable energy sources that are used as alternatives to non-renewable energy sources like coal and fossil fuels. In other words, in *Sultana's Dream* Rokeya was advocating for things like quality education for women, clean energy, and sustainable living practices (SDGs 4, 7, and 11) on a large scale in the early twentieth century. By prioritizing clean energy, sustainable communities, and environment-friendly approaches, the Queen of Ladyland (and Rokeya Sakhawat Hossain) was unknowingly advocating for climate action (SDG 13) as well.

The relationship between the women of Ladyland and nature as well as the environment is also telling. Instead of viewing nature and its resources as something they are entitled to and should exploit, the dwellers simply use knowledge to discover the wealth that “Nature has kept in store” (Hossain 14) for them. Nature is treated as an equal and an ally, not exploited, abused, and cast aside once its immediate purpose was fulfilled. The relationship with nature appears to be ongoing, and the Queen and her scientists seem to share some kind of innate kinship with nature and their surrounding environment. It is here that the ecofeminist perspective of the text becomes clear: firstly, the idea of the interconnectedness or “the depth to which human realities are embedded in ecological realities” (Cuomo 1), and secondly the conceptual connection between the patriarchal domination of both women and nature (Warren 125).

Moreover, Warren claims that ecological feminism provides a framework through which a feminist environmentalist ethic can be developed. The patriarchal domination of nature and women can be felt keenly in *Sultana's Dream*. The portrayal of

women as subalterns stowed away in their *zenanas*, and the reality of male dominion over females in colonial India has parallels to the domination and exploitation of nature through male-dominated policymakers in contemporary contexts. Thus, there is an inherent connection between “ecological degradation, sexism, and other forms of social oppression” (Cuomo 1). But *Ladyland* shows us that through subverting gender norms and the patriarchal structure, an alternative way of living can be achieved; one where an intuitive bond between people and the environment creates a sustainable and prosperous society, where the needs of the environment and nature are balanced with the needs of the citizens. The peace and lack of communal or international conflict in *Ladyland* can also be explained through ecofeminist perspectives as Warren (204) states that “an honest recognition of our commonalities and differences” can result in an intentional community without the violence that comes from unjustified dominion. This alternative community takes shape in the Queen’s approaches and initiatives regarding natural resources and the environment; she uses science to develop technology that assists nature instead of exploiting it and her vision of turning the country into an elaborate garden (Hossain 12) reflects an appreciation and awareness of nature and the environment.

In other words, *Sultana’s Dream* establishes the significance of quality education and scientific progress, as well as the need for top policymakers to enact initiatives that promote clean and sustainable energy sources, sustainable living, as well as the environment and climate-friendly processes that reflect an awareness of both the needs of nature and the relationship between ourselves and the environment. It also creates an ecofeminist framework through which contemporary environment-related

issues can be viewed and understood through the lens of patriarchal domination.

***Sultana's Dream* as a Roadmap for Achieving the SDGs**

Based on the discussion and theoretical framework established previously, it is apparent that *Sultana's Dream* works as some kind of prototype of the contemporary SDGs or Paris Accords. Written long before climate change and environmental destruction were declared major threats to the human race, the text can promote an environment-friendly and conscious attitude towards nature and the resources we consume and thus serve as a roadmap to achieving the SDGs.

Despite the magnitude of the risks of global warming, climate change, pollution, and environmental destruction, a large portion of the world's population refuses to accept this reality. Climate change denial is insidious due to the misinformation that is perpetuated by individuals or groups, and research carried out by McCright shows that 48.4% of adults who believe that the effects of global warming will never occur are conservative white males, with 74.2% the same demographic believing that the effects of global warming are often exaggerated (6). As such, education and awareness (SDG 4: Quality Education) are key tools for combatting ecological destruction and climate change.

In *Sultana's Dream*, the utopian Ladyland is possible because of its educated workforce and conscious citizens. Mookerjee-Leonard (146) argues that Rokeya Sakhawat was well aware of the "value of education as an instrument for challenging conformity to tyrannical customs imposed by patriarchy" and this was evident as Ladyland exemplified "the deployment of science and technology for the betterment of human life." The science-

loving Queen spearheaded change through her patronage of universities run by female scientists. Through the spread of education “far and wide among women” (Hossain 7), she protected her nation from foreign invasion and overturned the patriarchal domination of her society. Most importantly, she leveraged this educated workforce to move towards a more environmentally-conscious community. The scientists and thinkers of Ladyland developed innovative technology which in turn made things like clean water, affordable clean energy, sustainable communities, and by extension, climate action possible. Therefore, by depicting the lush, “ecologically sustainable and garden-like Ladyland” (Mookerjea-Leonard 147) as the result of an educated and enlightened population, we can say that Rokeya Sakhawat Hossain was prioritizing the need for quality education, advances in science, and innovative technology.

The text contains a plethora of scientific discoveries and technological inventions that enable a peaceful and comfortable life in Ladyland. Most of these resources make use of clean and renewable energy and have been made accessible and affordable to the general population. This corresponds to SDG 7 (Affordable and clean energy). These include the invention of a balloon attached to pipes that can draw water from the atmosphere for general use, which also prevented excess rain and storms (Hossain 12). This provided the population with a constant supply of clean water as well, including futuristic showers and taps (SDG 6: Clean water and sanitation). The scientists also invented an instrument that collected solar heat which could be distributed for cooking and heating. The women could cook with this heat from the sun, without the use of firewood or coal, so that no smoke or pollution

would result from the process (Hossain 7). An air car powered by electricity also appears in the text, as well as the use of electric power to till fields (Hossain 12). Because the nation relies on hydroelectric and solar power which are renewable and clean sources of energy, they have managed to create a sustainable and climate-resilient community, one where human, natural, and financial capital is well managed with adequate resources available for future use. This shows us that Ladyland has achieved SDG 11 (Sustainable cities and communities) by ensuring quality education, providing clean water, and using renewable and clean energy. Moreover, it is important to note that the inventions and instruments used are not ecologically destructive, and instead seem to work in tandem with nature, instead of working against it or exploiting it. Whether it is the air car, water balloon, or the storage of heat from sunlight, these innovations do almost no damage to the environment when compared to coal-powered vehicles, drilling for oil, and burning fossil fuels for heat/energy. The women of Ladyland seem to inherently understand the needs of nature, and acknowledge them along with their own needs, thus the relationship between the two is one of collaboration instead of one exploiting the other. This reflects the structural interconnection of women and nature in the capitalist patriarchal society as mentioned by Saleh (xi) and how women have the potential to make their communities safer because they are more likely to strike an ecological balance. As the women of Ladyland were once subjugated by the patriarchal systems, they are more intuitive about exploitative relationships and thus show consciousness and respect toward nature and the environment; they plant gardens, keep their cities clean, and focus more on helping nature yield its bounty instead of forcing nature to bend to their will. In other words, as Hasanat states, there is a harmonious

and balanced relationship between “science, women and environment” (121), where the citizens guide and control the climate and ecosystem. This shows a stark contrast between Rokeya’s approach and that of the current world: while the actions of the mostly male-dominated world have led to damage to the ecosystem and climate change, Ladyland’s approach proves that achieving SDGs 11 and 13 is possible only when we change our relationship with nature.

Through its policies that ensure clean water, clean energy, and sustainable living, Ladyland has attained the most pressing SDG of them all, SDG 13: Climate action. Due to the water balloon accumulating water for use, the nation has never suffered from a lack of rainwater or drought. Moreover, because the instrument is constantly drawing excess water from the environment, the citizens do not experience floods or thunderstorms (Hossain 12). Thus, they do not suffer from the extreme weather that comes from climate change/global warming. And in case of extreme heat, the citizens can simply use the excess water stored or use artificial fountains to keep temperatures cool.

Through the use of these instruments, as well as a reliance on sustainable resources, the Queen (the top policymaker of the nation) could ensure a high degree of climate management. The climate of Ladyland appears to be mild and moderate, maintained and managed by environment-friendly policies. It becomes clear, therefore, that focusing on clean water, sustainable and clean energy, and building sustainable communities make climate action more achievable, both in the context of the 19th century as well as the modern-day scenario we face.

In addition to serving as a blueprint for achieving the SDGs in today’s context, *Sultana’s Dream* outlines the role that

women have in protecting the environment and tackling climate change. In the text, the Queen appears as the catalyst for change, upending the capitalist patriarchal system and establishing a society that is more intuitive towards the needs of nature and the environment. She uses education to empower herself and other women, revolutionizing the way social and gender norms function and changing the nation's attitude and relationship with nature and its resources. As such, we can say that Rokeya is calling on women to stand up for the environment, to safeguard its resources in order to protect ourselves as well. From an ecofeminist perspective, the feminist movement and the ecological movement are aligned with a connection between the male domination of women and the "nonhuman biosphere" (Schultermandl 172-3), with both nature and women having been exploited for centuries by capitalist, male-dominated power structures. This also emphasizes the idea cemented by Tomar, that while women are a vulnerable and marginalized portion of society, it is this section that has the potential to be the "critical agent of change", and *Sultana's Dream* finds this to be especially true when it comes to the conservation of nature or sustainable, eco-friendly practices.

Thus, women (particularly female policymakers), have a pivotal role to play in combating climate change and achieving the SDGs mentioned throughout this paper. Women, therefore, have a responsibility to educate and empower themselves in order to advocate for their rights, as well as advocate for nature and the exploitation it has endured. Doing so will make it possible to achieve environment-related SDGs, and in turn, save the planet and humankind from irreversible destruction.

Conclusion

Living in the 21st century where people are already habituated to the comfort of technology, modernization, and urbanization, many have the idea that development and environmental sustainability cannot go together. Everyone is looking for a sustainable world where nature and humanity will cohabit, but at the same time, they do not want to compromise with the comfort that industrialization and urbanization have brought to the world. Rokeya Sakhawat Hossain's *Sultana's Dream* can definitely be a solution to this dichotomy and work as an example where it has been shown that development is possible in a sustainable way.

Sultana's Dream provides the picture-perfect world people are hoping to have in the near future. However, to achieve this, drastic actions must be taken to reduce the effect of the pollution of the earth at multiple levels. World leaders and policymakers need to be properly aware of the alarmed condition of environmental issues. As Sultana's waking up at the end of the story works at a symbolic level to represent the awakened consciousness of the women of 19th century India, if seen through the ecocritical landscape, it also invites the same consciousness regarding being compassionate to mother nature not only to the concerned people but the humanity in general.

As the risks of climate change are amplified with each passing decade, it becomes more important to spread this consciousness among people, and this can be seen with Greta Thunberg, a 21st-century climate activist and feminist who raises issues of climate change and environmental destruction with politicians and industrialists. Similar to the Queen of Ladyland, Thunberg appears to act as a visionary, attempting to enact change

to protect nature, and in turn secure a stable future for future generations. Moreover, many children's books have been written about Thunberg, portraying her work on climate change in a hero narrative, albeit "radical instantiations of this form" due to her identity as a young neurodivergent female (Moriarty 192). In the same vein, the Queen (and Rokeya Sakhawat Hossain) can also be considered a radical heroine due to their roles as females in an extremely patriarchal society in the 19th-century Indian subcontinent.

The current study is expected to have a clear impact on the stakeholders at multiple levels. Researchers who are working and relentlessly trying to improve the world environment for the better can look into the short story to attain a distinctive perspective. The policymakers may also look into the study to know about their contributory roles in transforming the fast-paced modern world into a world of sustainable development.

There are also multiple opportunities for further research in the area. Researchers can compare the *zenana* of *Sultana's Dream* to the female-led countries of the world. Currently, there are many countries that are led by female leaders who can be compared to the Queen of the 'Ladyland'. Interesting findings may show if female leaders are more prone to forming policies on environmental issues and thus contributing to the sustainable world that humanity is looking forward to.

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